

Supplementary Table 1: List of all antibodies used in Immunohistochemistry and Immunocytochemistry.

Primary Antibody	Dilution	Incubation	Secondary Antibody
PW1 (Gifted by David Sassoon, Inserm, Paris)	1:3000	Overnight at 4°C	Cy 3 Donkey anti-Rabbit (Stratech)
Laminin (Sigma)	1:50	1 Hour at 37°C	Alexa Fluor 594 Donkey anti-Chicken (Stratech)
Sca-1 (Abcam)	1/50	1 hour at 37°	Alexa Fluor 488 Donkey anti-Rat (Stratech)
Sox2 (Santa Cruz)	1/50	1 hour at 37°	Dylight 488 Donkey anti-Goat (Stratech)
Nanog (Abcam)	1/50	1 hour at 37°	Alexa Fluor 488 Donkey anti- Rabbit (Stratech)
Oct3/4 (Santa Cruz)	1/50	1 hour at 37°	FITC Donkey anti-Mouse IgG (Stratech)
Pax7 (DSHB)	1/50	1 hour at 37°	FITC Donkey anti-Mouse IgG (Stratech)
CD45 (Santa Cruz)	1/50	1 hour at 37°	Alexa Fluor 594 Donkey anti-Rat (Stratech)
α -sarc (Sigma)	1/50	1 hour at 37°	Dylight 594 Donkey anti-Mouse IgM (Stratech)
MHC (Sigma)	1/50	1 hour at 37°	Cy3 Donkey anti-Mouse IgG (Stratech)
SMA (Sigma)	1/500	1 hour at 37°	Cy3 Donkey anti-Mouse IgG (Stratech)
Calponon (Sigma)	1/50	1 hour at 37°	Cy 3 Donkey anti-Rabbit (Stratech)
Desmin (Santa Cruz)	1/50	1 hour at 37°	Cy3 Donkey anti-Mouse IgG (Stratech)
vWF Millipore	1/50	1 hour at 37°	Alexa Fluor 488 Donkey anti-Rabbit (Stratech)
CK18 Abcam	1/50	1 hour at 37°	FITC Donkey anti-Mouse IgG (Stratech)
CK19 Santa Cruz	1/50	1 hour at 37°	Dylight 488 Donkey anti-Goat (Stratech)
ChAT Abcam	1/50	1 hour at 37°	Alexa Fluor 488 Donkey anti-Rabbit (Stratech)
GFAP Dako	1/50	1 hour at 37°	Alexa Fluor 488 Donkey anti-Rabbit (Stratech)
β 3-Tubulin Abcam	1/50	1 hour at 37°	FITC Donkey anti-Mouse IgG (Stratech) or Cy3 Donkey anti-Mouse IgG (Stratech)
γ -Enolase Santa Cruz	1/50	1 hour at 37°	Dylight 488 Donkey anti-Goat (Stratech)
GFP (Abcam)	1/50	1 hour at 37°	Alexa Fluor 488 Donkey anti- Rabbit or HRP Donkey anti-Rabbit (Santa Cruz) (Stratech)
α FP (Life Technologies)	1/50	1 hour at 37°	Cy3 Donkey anti-Mouse IgG (Stratech)